

IMPROVING THE TEACHING METHODS OF LIFE SAFETY BASICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6777884>

This article explains the content of the safety of life activities, the importance of safety measures during human life and activities. At the same time, it is about training as a science of safety of life activity, its function, purpose and provision of security measures put before it. Terms such as security, activities, methods of ensuring the safety of life activities and their development are clearly defined. The article reflects the decisions adopted by our country on all technical, economic, political and information types of security measures in Uzbekistan, as well as the reforms implemented. The methods of explaining the concept of security in human life to young people today, ways and methods of integrating the positive and negative sides of the external influencers into the younger generation in the process of youth education, ways and methods of creating an atmosphere of risk and danger, as well as methods of developing the existing conditions, have been extensively analyzed. Further suggestions were made as a conclusion using the general analyzed data.

Keywords: Safety of life activity, risk, activity, technic risk, safety, vital activity, model of vital activity, principles of ensuring safety of activity, homo sphere.

Introduction. The sum of the active actions of a person - denotes the concept of activity. This is exactly the same activity that makes people different from other living beings. So, activity is a necessary indicator for the existence of a person. And labor is the highest form of human activity. Therefore, without both activity and labor, there will be no personality society. Below, in fact, we will clarify the concepts of vital activity, risk and security: activity is the process of purposeful interaction of nature and anthropogen environment with man in order to achieve a certain degree of economic effect.

Danger is the negative properties of living or dead matter that harm human health, nature and material wealth, lead to unfortunate and unpleasant phenomena.

Safety is a condition in which the flow of various substances, materials, energy and data affecting an object does not exceed the maximum allowable amount. Any risk is considered a real risk only when it is exposed to a specific object. When we say an object protected from the flow of various risks, it is possible to understand any component of the environment, namely: man, Society, State, organization (Enterprise, Institution), nature, World, Space.

Vital activity is a person's daily activity, rest, way of life. Security is a state of activity, which is the elimination of the occurrence of risks with a certain probability. Safety of activities from ancient times to the present is one of the most important aspects of the scientific and practical interests of mankind. Man always strives to ensure his own safety. With the development of production, these issues require special knowledge. In our time, security problems have become more acute. It is known that from unfortunate events, fires, accidents, a large amount of damage is caused. Therefore, it is important to educate people on the issues of protection against risks. This science plays an important social role in the stabilization of our society and contributes immensely to the increase in the level of security of the activities of the national economy. In this case, the software tools that are specifically made with decisions in this area, occupy a special place.

It can be said that the model of the process of activity consists of two elements: a person and an environment, since only people are engaged in active activity and they are in close relationship with the surrounding environment. Also, the system of "Man-environment" can be viewed as two purposes: the first purpose - when a person tries to achieve certain achievements, efficiency in the process of his labor activity, the second purpose - is to eliminate unpleasant consequences that arise in the process of his labor. At present, the maintenance of human life activities from production risks, natural disasters, disasters and catastrophes is one of the most urgent problems.

The preservation of human life activity from various disasters, disasters and disasters is one of the goals of the science of "safety of life activity". It is here that the science of "safety of life activity" studies the solution of these problems. The central focus of the science of "safety of life activity" lies on the goals of the development of "human - natural community". The science of safety of life activity is one of the scientific methodological disciplines, its main purpose is to create safe working conditions, to protect citizens from natural, technological and environmental emergencies, to prepare them for both theoretical and practical protection, as well as to teach the rules for providing medical care to the injured. The main tasks of the science of safety of life activity:

1. To examine the identification of risks. In this is a study of the causes of the occurrence of risks in the process of human activity, its features and unpleasant consequences.
2. To examine measures aimed at creating safe working conditions in production processes and service sectors. Education and Innovation Studies;

3. Development of methodologies that reduce occupational diseases in manufacturing processes;
4. To educate citizens on methods of protection against various hazards, natural disasters, accidents and accidents.
5. Prevention of Unfortunate Events in the labor processes study of Scorpions.
6. Carrying out rescue and restoration work of citizens in natural, technological and environmental damage furnaces.
7. Teaching people who have been injured to provide first aid.

Principles of ensuring the safety of activities principles of ensuring safety (principles) are conditionally divided into 4 classes, depending on the signs of their implementation:

1. Guiding (approximate) principle;
2. Technical principle;
3. Organizational principle;
4. Management principle.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be noted that ensuring security is not only a one-step process, but also a common task in which cooperation is carried out together. First of all, it is necessary for the population to consciously understand what is the safety of young and old life activities and to constantly follow these safety measures. Not only in this regard, the chain of interaction with labor activity, nature, the environment is also felt from the most basic issues of non-harmfulness. As long as human nature is interrelated, human activity is influenced by economic, political, technological, or hydrometreological aspects. As an independent educated person, I would have offered a wide range of explanations to the population in the field of development of security of life activity, as well as carrying out profilactics. After all, I hope that this will also serve as the main base for the younger generation of maturing.

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